

A CASE STUDY OF INSECT PESTS RESPONSIBLE FOR MASS DECLINE OF CITRUS PRODUCTION IN MANIPUR AND THEIR CONTROL REMEDIES

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ABSTRACT: The present study revealed that the trunk borer (high), the leaf miner (low), citrus psylla (medium), red scale (low), mealy bugs (low), lemon butterfly (low), black fly (medium), fruit sucking moth (low), citrus looper (low) and black aphids (medium) were witnessed as important insect pests of Mandarin orange in Manipur. These pests significantly attribute towards the citrus decline in the state. Further the results indicated that management of these insect pests, diagnosis of the causes of citrus decline, the rejuvenation schedule could be formulated with multi-disciplinary approaches like proper spacing, sanitation, regulate the vegetative growth by proper scheduling of irrigation and fertilizer application, growing curry leaf (*Murraya koenigii*) plant as collateral host in the vicinity of citrus orchards since it acts as breeding site for psylla, removal of water shoots regularly to restrict leaf miner, black fly, incidence since it survives on these water shoots during off season, placing yellow sticky traps whitefly, black fly & leaf miner control, sticky bands on the trunk portion of the tree to prevent the climbing of mealy bug crawlers, raking of tree basins during April-May exposes fruit fly pupae to harsh climate and natural enemies, followed by application of either T₁-Zorba (fenbucarb 20% + buprofezin 5%) 25 SE @ 30 ml/15 litres of water + Fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK, T₂= Tabuz (buprofezin 15% + acephate 35%) 50 WP @ 30 ml/15 litres of water + fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK, T₃-Acephate 70 SP @ 30 gm @ 30 ml/15 litres of water + fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK and T₄-Thiamethoxam 75 WG @ 30/15 litres of water + fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK with a record of high, moderate, moderate and moderate effectiveness, respectively, three times first at young flush during Spring (February-March), 2nd during Summer (June-July) and 3rd during Winter (October-November) with combination of fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with ITK (Indigenous Technical Knowledge) and agronomic practices which can be used to check citrus decline in NE region in general and Manipur in particular recording high and moderate effectiveness against the major insect pests of citrus.

Key words: Case study, Citrus, Insect pests, Management, Manipur

INTRODUCTION

In India, citrus is commercially grown in about 10.42 lakh hectares with an annually production of 100.90 lakh tones and productivity of 9.7 t/ha and are primarily grown in Manipur, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh, Punjab, Karnataka, Uttaranchal, Bihar, Odisha, Assam and Gujarat. The fruit crop is of particular interest because of its high content of Vitamin C and refreshing juice. Of the various types of citrus fruits grown in India, orange (Mandarin or Sandra), sweet orange (mosambi) are lime/lemon are of commercial importance. North Eastern Region is one of the richest reservoirs of genetic diversity of citrus as well as the secondary centre of origin of numerous citrus species and has been

described as one of the major centre of diversity for citrus in both wild and cultivated forms (SINGH *et al.*, 2006). The various factors attribute to declining the citrus in India, where insect pests are major one. In India, 250 species of insects and mites have been reported inflicting different species of citrus (NATH and DEKA, 2019). The trunk borer the leaf miner, the citrus psylla, the red scale, the mealy bugs, the black fly, citrus looper and the black aphid are equally important and damages at nursery and plants during each new flush. Other pests of minor importance *viz.*, lemon butterfly, leaf miner, looper, tobacco caterpillars, leaf folder, mealy bugs, scales. Orange shoot borer, bark eating caterpillar, fruit sucking moths and fruit flies etc. were also occurred on the fruit crop (AZAD THAKUR *et al.*, 2012). For the last five-six years, in Manipur mass decline has been occurred, thus the present case study proposed to investigate the key insect pests and their management practices.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Case studies on survey of insect pests responsible in citrus decline and their effective management strategies in Manipur were carried out the by selected five locations in each of five hill districts *viz.*, Tamenglong, Senapati, Ukhrul, Senapati and Churachanpur using randomized block design (RBD). Insect pests study was conducted by selecting five locations each in the districts during 2017-2020. In a location, 25 plants were selected, each block comprised of 5 plants that was considered as one replication. Accordingly, management practices were evaluated in the plants selected in each replication using new molecular chemical insecticides, agronomic practices and Indigenous Technical Knowledge (ITK) techniques. The details of the materials and methods adopted are given below:

Insect pest identification: The record of pest complex of citrus was done by the collection of different stages such as egg, nymph and adults present on the leaves. The insect samples were put in alcohol (70%) for their identification at a later date. The insect pests were identified up to generic level under a stereoscopic light microscope in the laboratory. The illustrated diagnostic keys of MARTIN *et al.* (2000) and GULLAN (2000) were consulted to confirm the identification of whitefly and mealy bug and other insect pests.

Field evaluation of pesticides, agronomic practices and ITK against the pests:

The treatments comprised of:

T₁=Zorba (fenbucarb 20% + buprofezin 5%) 25 SE @ 30 ml/15 litres of water + Fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK;

T₂= Tabuz (buprofezin 15% + acephate 35%) 50 WP @ 30 ml/15 litres of water + fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK;

T₃=Acephate 70 SP @ 30 gm @ 30 ml/15 litres of water + fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK;

T₄=Thiamethoxam 75 WG @ 30 per 15 litres of water+ fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK;

T₅=Zorba (fenobucarb 20% + buprofezin 5%) 25 SE @ 30 ml/15 litres of water;

T₆=Tabuz (buprofezin 15% + acephate 35%) 50 WP @ 30 ml/15 litres of water,

T₇=Acephate 70 SP @ 30 gm @ 30 ml/15 litres of water,

T₈=Thiamethoxam 75 WG @ 30 per 15 litres of water,

T₉=Fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK.

T₁₀ untreated control.

The application of the treatments on 5 plants infested by the insect pests was considered as one replication & there were 5 replications in each location. The spraying on

citrus plantation was done 3 times during February-March, June-July and October-November for four consecutive experimental years viz., 2017, 2018, 2019 and 2020 using Rocker sprayer and later sprayed plants were tagged and observation was made on infestation on 20/04/2017, 06/09/2017, 20/04/2018, 06/09/2018, 20/04/2019, 20/09/2019, 20/04/2020 and 20/09/2020, respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The significant findings generated from the present case study on insect pests mainly involving in mass citrus decline in Manipur and their control remedies conducted during 2018-19, are briefly documented and discussed below:

(A). Important insect pests recorded during survey in citrus at Manipur:

In the study period of three years (2017 to 2020), we encountered eleven significant insect pests infesting the citrus plantation (Table 1). The recorded insect pests were identified at generic-level as the trunk borer (high), the leaf miner (low), citrus psylla (medium), red scale (low), mealy bugs (low), lemon butterfly (low), black fly (medium), fruit sucking moth (low), citrus looper (low) and black aphids (medium) (Table-1). Species-level identification was not done due to unavailability of materials needed to study the specimens at higher magnification as well as limited availability of literature resources. However, the present findings encouraged by the reports of (Hussain *et al.*, 2017) who observed the five most significant insect pests infesting the citrus plantation. The recorded insect pests were identified at generic-level as woolly whitefly (*Aleurothrixus* sp.), cottony cushion scale (*Icerya purchasi*), citrus leaf miner (*Phyllocnistis* sp.), diaspine black scale (*Parlatoria* sp.) and brown scale (*Coccus* sp.) on citrus.

Table-1: Insect pests of citrus recorded and their incidence

S.No.	Insect pest	Order: Family	Incidences
1.	Trunk borer, <i>Aoplophora versteegi</i> Ritsema	Coleoptera: Cerambycidae	4.5-49.65%
2.	Bark eating caterpillar, <i>Inderbella tetraonis</i>	Lepidoptera: Metarbelidae	20.50-45.75%
3.	Leaf miner, <i>Phyllocnistis citrella</i> Stainton	Lepidoptera: Gacillaridae	9.56-44.55%
4.	Lemon butterfly, <i>Papilio demoleus</i> Linn.	Lepidoptera: Papilionidae	5.50-28.24%
5.	Citrus psylla, <i>Diaphornia citrii</i> Kuw.	Hemiptera: Psyllidae	4.40-10.12%
6.	Citrus black Aphid, <i>Toxoptera aurantii</i> Boyen	Hemiptera: Aphidididae	10.57-15.45%
7.	Citrus looper, <i>Anacamptodes fragilaria</i> Wikipedia	Lepidoptera: Geometridae	4.50-14.25%
8.	Citrus mealy bug, <i>Pseudococcus filamentosus</i> Cockerell	Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae	3.10-4.55%
9.	Citrus black fly, <i>Aleurocanthus it woglumi</i> Ashby	Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae	4.20-18.40%
10.	Fruit sucking moth, <i>Othereis fullonia</i> Cramer	Lepidoptera: Noctuidae	3.15-12.50%
11.	Citrus red scale, <i>Aonidiella aurantii</i> Maskell	Hemiptera: Diaspididae	1.15-2.50%

(B) Nature of damage of major insect pest of citrus:

S.No.	Insect Pest	Damage
1.	Citrus trunk borer	Grub bores into the pith making round holes generally at the base of the trunk. Accumulation of coarse saw dust in tree base. Grub destroys the xylem and phloem during their long development period causing the deterioration of the tree resulting in serious economic losses. About 15-60% damage caused in citrus damage in Khasi mandarin.
2.	Bark eating caterpillar	Infest bark of young and matured citrus plant. Larvae make tunnel at the joints of trunk or branches and feed on the bark during night. Heavy infestation leads to slowly drying of plant due to nutrient deficiency. Heavy infestation leads to slowly drying of plant due to nutrient deficiency. Attacked tree gradually declines.
3.	Lemon butterfly	Citrus butterfly is a pest of nurseries and young plantations. Caterpillar feeds on foliage causing defoliation. Most destructive stage is larva. Young larval stage looks like bird excreta.
4.	Leaf miner	Mostly important in nursery and young orchard. Larval stage is more destructive. Newly emerged larva mines the under surface of the leaf in a zigzag way. Appearance of silvery serpentine mines on the underside of leaf which leads to wrinkling and curling up. Leaf miner attacks helps in spreading mealy bug infestation and predisposes to Canker infection.
5.	Citrus Psylla	Peak period for multiplication is in May. Both nymph and adult sucks the cell sap from newly emerged leaves, tender shoots and flowers causing curling of leaves and defoliation leading to deblossoming and dieback. The pest is responsible for the greening disease of citrus. Secretes whitish crystalline honeydew which attracts the growth of fungus, adversely affecting the photosynthesis. Psylla is also known to inject toxin in plant causing die-back of shoot. It acts as vector of citrus greening virus disease.
6.	Citrus looper	Drooping and hanging from trees/ upper branch through silken threads. Looper larva voraciously consume new growth flushes resulting in severe defoliation, but also feed on blossoms and young fruits. Very young larvae typically feed on lower leaf surfaces along the leaf margin. Mature larvae eat the leaves making holes on it or consume them entirely. It is an emerging pest.
7.	Citrus black aphid	Nymph and adult suck the sap from tender parts of plant and devitalize. Nymphs excrete honeydew on which black sooty mould grows wildly resulting in blackening of the twig. In severe infestation the flowers do not form fruits. The pest responsible for vectoring citrus virus disease 'Tristeza'.
8.	Citrus black fly	The cell sap is suck from the leaves leading to leaf curling, leaves fall off immaturely. Honey dew secretion leads to sooty mould fungus. Leaf turns to black in colour and affects photosynthetic activity of the leaves. Affected trees produce few blossoms which develop into insipid fruits.
9.	Fruit sucking moth	It is a serious pest of maturing khasi mandarin fruits. Adult is the damaging stage. The adults puncture the ripening fruits. Such fruits drop prematurely, As a result of rotting due to fungal and bacterial infections introduced through punctures causing considerable fruit loss.
10.	Citrus red scale	The red scales attack all aerial parts of the tree including twigs, leaves, branches, and fruit by sucking on the plant tissues with their long, filamentous mouthparts. Severe infestations cause leaf yellowing and drop, dieback of twigs and limbs, and occasionally death of the tree. Tree damage is most likely to occur in late summer and early fall when scale populations are highest and moisture stress on the tree is greatest.
11.	Citrus mealy bug	Both nymphs and adults suck the sap from the cells of tender branches and fruits turn pale colour. Affected plant parts wilt and dry up. Large amounts of honey dew excrete - sooty mould fungus. Fungus covers the foliage and fruits. In severe infestation the flowers do not form fruits.

(C) Seasonal incidence of recorded insect pests

During the survey period altogether eleven insect pests were associated with extensive damage of citrus, out of which, trunk borer, leaf miner, bark eating caterpillar, leaf miner, lemon butterfly, citrus black fly, citrus black Aphid, citrus looper, fruit sucking moth and citrus psylla were observed as major pests of mandarin orange in Manipur hilly areas (Table-1). These pests significantly contribute towards the citrus decline in the state peak period of activities were noticed from June-July for Trunk borer, May-June for leaf miner, June-July for lemon butterfly, June-August for citrus black fly, January-February for citrus black Aphid and July-August for citrus looper, October-November for fruit sucking moth and May-June for citrus psylla with infestation on citrus tree basis being, 49.65, 45.75, 44.55, 28.24, 18.40, 15.45, 14.25, 12.50 and 10.12%, respectively (Table 2).

Table-2: Seasonal incidence of the most important insect pests of citrus

S.No.	Insect Pest	Emergence	Peak season	Disappear
1.	Trunk borer	April	June-July	November
2.	Bark eating caterpillar	November	May- June	July
3.	Leaf miner	April	June- July	January
4.	Lemon butterfly	April	June- July	January
5.	Citrus psylla	January first week	May-June	Dec. middle week
6.	Citrus looper	April	July - August	December
7.	Citrus black fly	April	June- August	November
8.	Black citrus Aphid	December	January-February	June
9.	Fruit sucking moth	September	Oct.-November	February

Field evaluation of insecticides along with ITK practices

The results on field evaluation of ten treatments including one control revealed that out of treatment combinations Zorba (fenobucarb 20% + buprofezin 5%) 25 SE @ 30 ml/15 litres of water + fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK (T₁) proved to be the most effective in controlling almost all the major insect pests with high effectiveness against the major insect pests. It was followed by (T₂) Tabuz (Buprofezin 15% + Acephate 35%) 50 WP @ 30 ml/15 litres of water along with ITK & agronomic practices, (T₃), Acephate 70 SP @ 30 gm @ 30 ml/15 litres of water + fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK and (T₄) Thiamethoxam 75 WG @ 30 per 15 litres of water+ fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK each giving moderate effectiveness against the pests. The least effective was observed in the treatment with fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK (T₉), recording very less effectiveness against the pests recording highest incidence (T₁) (Table-3).

Table-3: Relative effectiveness of the various treatments against the major insect pests in citrus the study period of 2017-2020 (Pooled data)

Treatment	Particular	Status of effectiveness
T ₁ =	Zorba (fenbucarb 20% + buprofezin 5%) 25 SE @ 30 ml/15 litres of water + Fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK	High
T ₂ =	Tabuz (buprofezin 15% + acephate 35%) 50 WP @ 30 ml/15 litres of water + fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK	Moderate
T ₃ =	Acephate 70 SP @ 30 gm @ 30 ml/15 litres of water + fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK	Moderate
T ₄ =	Thiamethoxam 75 WG @ 30 per 15 litres of water+ fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices & ITK	Moderate
T ₅ =	Zorba (fenbucarb 20% + buprofezin 5%) 25 SE @ 30 ml/15 litres of wate	Slightly effective
T ₆ =	Tabuz (buprofezin 15% + acephate 35%) 50 WP @ 30 ml/15 litres of water	Slightly effective
T ₇ =	Acephate 70 SP @ 30 gm @ 30 ml/15 litres of water	Less effective
T ₈ =	Thiamethoxam 75 WG @ 30 per 15 litres of water	Less effective
T ₉ =	fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices& ITK	Very less effective
T ₀ =	Control	Shown non effectiveness

Calender of operations of citrus growers to be adopted

January: In case there is infestation of Bark eating caterpillar then remove the wooden frass present in between the joints of the tree trunk and inject Dichlorvos (DDVP) 76 SL @ 5 ml/lit. of water into the larval tunnel with the help of disposable syringe and push the cotton swab soaked in the solution of Copper Oxychloride 50 WP @ 2 gm/litre of water in the larval tunnel. Prune dead wood from the trees. While pruning dip the pruning instruments in 1% sodium hypochlorite solution. Smoking has to be taken up as it acts as repellent the insect pests of citrus.

February: During this month heavy incidence of citrus leaf miner, citrus psylla and black fly is observed, spray the plants with either Zorba (fenbucarb 20% + buprofezin 5%) 25 SE @ 30 ml/15 litres of water or Tabuz (buprofezin 15% + acephate 35%) 50 WP @ 30 ml/15 litres of water by Rocking sprayer. Fish water to attract predatory ant + smoking with agronomic practices. Application of Bordeaux mixture (2:2:250) has to be done. In case there is infestation of Bark eating caterpillar then remove the wooden frass present in between the joints of the tree trunk and inject Dichlorvos (DDVP) 76 SL @ 5 ml in the larval tunnel with the help of disposable syringe and push the cotton swab soaked in Copper oxychloride 50 WP @ 2 gm/lit. of water solution in the larval tunnel. **Smoking has to be taken up as it acts as repellent the insect pests of citrus.** Extracts of *Vitex nigundo*, *Artemisia nilagirica*, *Melia azadirach* etc. can also used for the control of citrus psylla.

March: In case of citrus psylla and leaf miner attack spray with either Zorba (fenbucarb 20% + buprofezin 5%) 25 SE @ 30 ml/15 litres of water or Tabuz (buprofezin 15% + acephate 35%) 50 WP @ 30 ml/15 litres of water. Repeat the spray after 15 days. Apply Bordeaux mixture (2:2:250 of Copper Sulphate, Lime and Water) during March to the plats. Grow sunflower and marigold in the periphery of citrus orchard to attract the population of predators like syrphid, predatory mite, lacewing, minute pirate bug, samsel bug and ladybird beetle. In case of leaf eating caterpillar infestation spray Dimethoate 30 EC @ 2ml/litre of water. During this month due to rise in temperature drip irrigation should be given @ 12-53, 78-127, and 145-180 litres per day for trees 1-4, 5-7,8 years old and above respectively. Follow double ring method of irrigation and irrigate orchard 7 to 10 days.

April: During April month, incidence of bark eating caterpillar is commonly seen, more menacing on old orchards. To control the pest, remove the wooden frass and then inject Dichlorvos (0.1%) at the rate of 5 ml with the help of disposable syringe, or push the Dichlorvos soaked cotton wet into the larval tunnel and plug with muddy soil the opening. Smoking in the field may be for black fly control. About 50% eggs are laid by the citrus black fly and hatch during the 2nd half of April month. The nymphs and adults of citrus psylla both suck cell sap from young leaves and twigs. The nymphs secrete honeydew on which black sooty mold develops on entire tree which is called 'Kolshi'. Hence, to control the pest, spray of Zorba (fenbucarb 20% + buprofezin 5%) 25 SE @ 30 ml/15 litres of water or Tabuz (buprofezin 15% + acephate 35%) 50 WP @ 30 ml/15 litres of water. Repeat the spray after 15 days.

May: Irrigation should be continued to maintain the fruit set. Give water stress to tree for preparing them for the next crop in June. Apply Bordeaux paste on the tree trunk upto the height of 24 inches by brush. For preparation of Bordeaux paste dissolve 1 kg Copper sulphate in 5 liters water in a plastic bucket and 1 kg slaked Lime in 5 litres water in separate bucket leave it for a overnight. Next day mix them together to make a paste. Apply the paste on tree trunk with in 12 hours after mixing. The menace of Bark eating caterpillar can be checked in this month by removing the wooden frass and they injecting Dichlorvos 76 EC 0.1% @ 5 ml in a larval tunnel with the help of disposable syringe or pushing in the Dichlorvos 76 EC 0.1% soaked cotton wool into the larval tunnel. For controlling citrus Mealy bugs the basin around the tree trunk should be earth on up. Sticky band by smearing with mobil oil around the tree trunk and destruction of ant's nests should be done. Spraying of Chlorpyrifos 20 EC @ 2 ml/litre of water or Dichlorvos 76 EC @ 2.5 ml/litre of water should be done on the tree leaves and trunk. Snail infestation in certain pockets has been observed recently on citrus. To control snails use metaldehyde pellets. Alternatively take straw of paddy or wheat, jaggery or sugarcane mollasses, yeast and thiamethaxam 25 WG. In order to prepare poison bait dissolve 2 kg jaggery, 25 gms yeast in 10 litre water. Now add wheat of paddy husk and mix well and keep for fermentation for 10 to 12 hrs. Thereafter add 100 gm Methomyl 40 SP or 50 gms thiamethaxam 25 WG and spread it at the base of citrus tree trunk in the evening through out the entire orchards. Citrus snail will be attracted and will die after feeding on such poison bait.

June: In case the trees on stress receives water during stress period, Cycocel a growth retardant at the rate of one gm per litre of water should be sprayed on the trees. Second spray should be applied after 20 days. For increasing the fruit size of Ambia crop and if there is wide gap of more than a week between two spell of rains spray potassium nitrate at the rate of 1.5 kg + 2, 4, D 1.5 gms per 100 litres of water. Application of fish water at the base of the

citrus plant is to attract predatory red tree ant (*Oecophylla* sp.) to control citrus trunk borer. To control the trunk borer, application of Zorba (fenbucarb 20% + buprofezin 5%) 25 SE @ 30 ml/15 litres of water or Tabuz (buprofezin 15% + acephate 35%) 50 WP @ 30 ml/15 litres of water is suggested with second spray to be given after 15 days.

July: Avoid water stagnation near the tree trunk. Drain out excess rainwater from the orchard through the drainage channels prepared earlier. Remove water shoots and any other shoots below the budded area. Intercrops such as Urad, Moong, Soyabean, Groundnut etc. can be grown in between the interspaces of plants. For green manuring sow seeds of Dhaincha or sun hemp @ 40 kg per hectare. Apply fish water at the base of the citrus plant to control citrus trunk borer.

August: Avoid water stagnation near the tree trunk. Stagnated water should be disposed off through the drain, clean the drains if required. Remove water shoots from the trees. If necessary, spray of Zorba (fenbucarb 20% + buprofezin 5%) 25 SE @ 30 ml/15 litres of water or Tabuz (buprofezin 15% + acephate 35%) 50 WP @ 30 ml/15 litres of water should be done to check the infestation of black fly and leaf miner. Repeat second round with the above insecticide after 10 days of first spray. During this month there is attack of fruit sucking moth. To control the pest destroy all the fallen fruits by burying in the pit. Poison baiting with 20 gms Malathion 25 WP or 50 ml Diazinon mixed with 200 g gur and some orange juice in two litres of water should be placed in a tray. Place a bulb of 60 watts above this tray to kill the moth. Follow clean cultivation and uproot all weeds in the orchard. Smoking below the citrus plant before flowering to control almost all the major insect pests is required.

September: Undertake necessary tillage operations if there are no rains. Remove the weeds from the tree basin and prepared double ring around the tree for irrigation. Care should be taken to see that first ring is made one meter away from trunk and second ring meter away from the trunk. In case of drip irrigation system spread the laterals and gives irrigation as per requirement. Control fruit sucking moth by preparing poison bait containing 20 g Malathion 25 WP or 50 ml Diazinon 20 EC mixed with 200 g gur and some orange juice in 2 liters of water. Fill it in as bottle and has one bottle between 25 to 30 trees all over the orchard. Create smoke in bearing orchard in the late evening hours i.e. 7.00 to 10.00 pm during the last fortnight before the harvest. To control fruit fly use male attracting traps containing 0.1 percent methyl eugenol and 0.05 per cent Malathion. Use 25 traps per hectare from 60 days before fruit harvest and change the bait after every 7 days. Follow clean cultivation in orchard and bury fallen fruits in a deep pit everyday.

October: Control Fruit sucking moth by preparing a poison bait containing 20 ml Malathion 50 EC or 50 ml Diazinon 20 EC mixed with 200 g gur (jaggery) or orange juice in 2 litre of water. Fill it in a broad mouth bottle and hang one bottle between 25 to 30 trees all over the orchard. Create smoke in orchard with grass (wet) cow dung cakes and neem leaves in the late evening hours i.e. 7.00 to 10.00 pm during this month. During this month, spray of Zorba (fenbucarb 20% + buprofezin 5%) 25 SE @ 30 ml/15 litres of water or Tabuz (buprofezin 15% + acephate 35%) 50 WP @ 30 ml/15 litres of water to check infestation of insect pests. Apply fish water at the base of the citrus plant to control citrus trunk borer. To control fruit fly use sex traps (methyl eugenol traps) for trapping the fruit flies containing 0.05 percent Malathion 50 EC mixed with orange juice one litre. Use 25 traps per hectare from 60 days before fruit harvest and change the bait after every 7 days. Follow clean cultivation in orchard and bury fallen fruit in a pit and cover it with soil every day. Apply post monsoon Bordeaux paste on the tree trunk. Weeding and harrowing operation should be done

in the orchard. Prepare double ring system for irrigation. Harvesting of matured santra fruit should be started.

November: In case of incidence of citrus mite spray Dicofol 18.5 EC at the rate of 1.5 ml or wettable sulphur at the rate of 3 gm per litre of water. After 15 days second application should be given with either of the two above Miticides (Do not repeat the miticide as far as possible). Apply Bordeaux paste on tree trunk if not applied earlier. Harvest the fruits; if delay is anticipated in harvesting of fruits, two sprays of Giberellic acid 15 ppm + urea 1% may be given at 15 days interval. Uproot and destroy all weeds. Breakdown the soil collected around the tree trunk.

December: In case of incidence of citrus mite spray Dicofol 18.5 EC at the rate of 1.5 ml or wettable sulphur at the rate of 3 gm per litre of water. After 15 days second application should be given with either of the two above Miticides (Do not repeat the Miticide as far as possible). During the first fortnight of this month spray of Zorba (fenbucarb 20% + buprofezin 5%) 25 SE @ 30 ml/15 litres of water or Tabuz (buprofezin 15% + acephate 35%) 50 WP @ 30 ml/15 litres of water should be done directing the spray nozzle on the underside of the leaves to check the infestation of black fly and leaf miner. Repeat application with any one of the insecticides not sprayed earlier after 15 days interval. For citrus leaf miner attack particularly in nursery pluck and destroy the affected leaves and sprays Spinosad 45 SC @ 0.5 ml or Quinalphos 25 EC @ 1.5 ml or Dimethoate 30 EC @ 2.0 ml in one litre water. Nurseryman should start budding on rootstock. Take care to do budding 20 to 25 cm above ground level.

Conclusion: From the present case study leads to conclusion that citrus is the most important valuable horticultural fruit crop grown in Manipur. However, there are a number of insect pests that are plaguing citrus plantation leading to economic loss in North-Eastern region in general and Manipur in particular. Out of these, the trunk borer, the leaf miner, citrus psylla, red scale, mealy bugs, lemon butterfly, black fly, fruit sucking moth, citrus looper and black aphids are considered as major insect pests. Their populations could be controlled by following package and practices such as application of either Zorba (fenbucarb 20% + buprofezin 5%) 25 SE @ 30 ml/15 litres of water or Tabuz (buprofezin 15% + acephate 35%) 50 WP @ 30 ml/15 litres of water along with agronomic and ITK practices based on calendar-wise operations generated from the case study in a year that will be helping in checking the mass decline of citrus in the state.

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